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Education as a Correlate of Family Planning among Couples in Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper investigated the influence of education on couples' knowledge of family planning. Using the quantitative design, 199 married men and 199 married women who resided in Etche Local Government Area of Rivers State, Nigeria were examined. The stratified random sampling technique was employed in the selection of the respondents. A self-structured questionnaire was used for collection of data. The reliability value of the questionnaire yielded 0.68. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the Z-test was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings showed that the couples had good knowledge of family planning ($x = 3.09$). Difference in levels of education had a statistical significant effect on the couples' knowledge of family planning ($p < 0.05$). Among the recommendations was that more awareness of family planning should be created in tertiary institutions through a general course of study.

Keywords: couples, education, family, planning.